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6. DETERMINANTS OF HOSPITALIZATION AMONG THE ELDERLY PEOPLE IN VOJVODINA

Sonja Čanković^{1,2}, Vesna Mijatović Jovanović^{1,2}, Dušan Čanković^{1,2}, Ivana Radić^{1,2}, Sanja Harhaji^{1,2}, Tanja Tomašević², Dragana Milijašević^{1,2}

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Objectives: Population of Vojvodina is very old, and projections indicate that by 2050 one in three persons will be older than 60 years. This study aimed to examine the socio-economic and health status factors associated with hospitalization among the elderly people.

Materials and methods: We analyzed data from the National Health Survey Serbia conducted in 2013. Study included 886 examinees (58% females and 42% males) aged 65 and over who were interviewed in Vojvodina. To analyze determinants of hospitalization two multivariate logistic regression models were implemented: model 1 included socio-economic variables and model 2 included socio-economic, life-style and health status variables.

Results: In past 12 months, 11.1% of respondents were hospitalized with average length of stay 12 days. Majority of hospitalized were males (14.2% vs 8.9%). In model 1, males had higher odds of hospitalization (OR=2.38; 95%CI=1.41-4.01), respondents with the lowest level of education (OR=2.82; 95%CI=1.03-7.72) and one who had out-of-pocket payments for outpatients health care (OR=3.71; 95%CI=1.59-8.66). In model 2, higher odds of hospitalization had males (OR=2.74; 95%CI=1.28-5.84) and one who assessed their health as poor (OR=2.90; 95%CI=1.06-7.87).

Conclusions: In this study we found several factors associated with hospitalization of elderly people in Vojvodina: gender, self-assessed health, educational level and out-of-pocket payments.

Key words: Aging, Health services, Hospitalization